

Mean Amplitudes of Vibration in Some Isotopic Species of Disulfur Monoxide

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The mean amplitudes of vibration of isotopic species of disulfur monoxides viz., $^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, $^{32}\text{S}_2^{18}\text{O}$, $^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, $^{34}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$ and $^{34}\text{S}^{32}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$ have been computed in the temp range 0-1000 K. The isotopic effect of sulphur and oxygen atoms over bonded S-S, S-O and non bonded S...O distances have been studied using Muller's method of characteristic vibration. Results are discussed in the light of molecular structure and bonding in disulfur monoxides.

THE existence of disulfur monoxide was characterised by Meschi and Myers¹ and Blukis and Myers² by mass and infrared spectroscopy about two decades ago. However, because of its very small existence and stability, its spectroscopic properties could not be reported for a long period. At the same time, this molecular species was thought to play an important role in many photochemical combustion and electric discharge reactions of sulfur and oxygen. Schenk and Steudel³ have shown that S_2O is one of the products formed from the very reactive SO species (reacting with itself), and is a good indicator for the prior existence of SO. Recently, Hopkins and coworkers⁴ reported the ir spectra of a natural abundance and isotopically enriched S_2O matrix isolated in argon and the bands for $^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, $^{32}\text{S}_2^{18}\text{O}$, $^{34}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, $^{34}\text{S}^{32}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$ and $^{32}\text{S}^{34}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$ have been assigned.

While dealing with the molecular structures, the authors⁴ have reported force constants namely K_{ss} , K_{so} and K_{α} , and other bond angle interaction force constants by using Wilson's FG matrix method. They also reproduced the vibrational frequencies of all the isotopic species. However, the mean amplitudes of vibration for these isotopic species were not reported. Hence, the object of the present study is to report mean amplitudes of vibrations for S-S bonds, S-O bonds and S...O bonds and discuss the results in terms of isotopic effect.

Theoretical considerations: For asymmetrical disulfur monoxide and its isotopes viz., $^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, $^{32}\text{S}_2^{18}\text{O}$, $^{34}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, $^{32}\text{S}^{34}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$ and $^{34}\text{S}^{32}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$ mean amplitudes of vibrations were computed on the basis of C_s point group symmetry. The vibrational representation for this group is $\Gamma = 3A'$. The three dimensional secular equation $|\Sigma G^{-1} - \Delta E| = 0$

of Cyvin⁵ was solved for calculating Σ values by Muller's L-matrix approximation method⁶.

G-matrices:

The kinetic energy matrices for XYZ (C_s) type molecules⁷ are as under:

$$G_{11} = \mu_x + \mu_y, \quad G_{12} = G_{21} = \mu_x \cos \alpha, \quad G_{13} = G_{31} = \left(\frac{r_1}{r_2}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \times \mu_x \sin \alpha, \quad G_{22} = \mu_x + \mu_z, \quad G_{23} = G_{32} = \left(\frac{r_2}{r_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \mu_x \sin \alpha, \quad G_{33} = \left[\left(\frac{r_1}{r_2}\right) + \left(\frac{r_2}{r_1}\right) - 2 \cos \alpha\right] \mu_x + \frac{r_2}{r_1} \mu_y + \frac{r_1}{r_2} \mu_z.$$

The following geometrical parameters⁸ are used:

$$r_{SO} = 1.4594 \text{ \AA}, \quad r_{SS} = 1.8845 \text{ \AA} \text{ and } \angle_{SSO} = 118.08^\circ$$

Σ -matrices:

For XYZ (C_s) symmetry, if the frequencies are: $\nu_1 = \nu_{XY}$, $\nu_2 = \nu_{XZ}$ and $\nu_3 = \nu_{XYZ}$, the Σ elements are:

$$\Sigma_{11} = G_{11} \Delta_1, \quad \Sigma_{12} = G_{12} \Delta_1, \quad \Sigma_{13} = G_{13} \Delta_1$$

$$\Sigma_{22} = \frac{\Delta_1 G_{12}^2 + \Delta_2 A}{G_{11}}$$

$$\Sigma_{23} = \frac{\Delta_1 G_{12} G_{13} + \Delta_2 B}{G_{11}}$$

$$\Sigma_{33} = \frac{\Delta_1 G_{13}^2 + \Delta_2 B^2 + \Delta_3 \det |G|}{G_{11} A + \frac{\Delta_3 \det |G|}{A}}$$

$$\text{Here } \Delta = \frac{h}{8\pi^2 \nu^2 C} \cot h \left(\frac{h\nu}{KT} \right);$$

$$A = G_{11} G_{22} - G_{12}^2$$

$$B = G_{11} G_{23} - G_{12} G_{13}$$

$$\det |G| = AG_{33} - BG_{23} + CG_{13}$$

$$\text{where } C = G_{12} G_{23} - G_{13} G_{22}$$

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(ii) *Mean square amplitudes* : The mean square amplitude quantities σ_{r_1} and σ_{r_2} for bonded atoms pair X-Y and Y-Z, respectively are :

$$\sigma_{r_1} = \Sigma_{11}, \quad \sigma_{r_2} = \Sigma_{22}$$

σ_{α} , the quantity due to \widehat{XYZ} bending and other quantities are the respective interactions and are as follows :

$$\sigma_{\alpha} = \Sigma_{33}, \quad \sigma_{r_1 r_2} = \Sigma_{12}, \quad \sigma_{r_1 \alpha} = \Sigma_{13} \text{ and } \sigma_{r_2 \alpha} = \Sigma_{23}$$

The quantity σ_i due to the non-bonded atom pair X...Z may be obtained as a linear combination of other quantities due to bonded atom pairs bending of the molecules. The expression for the σ_i is :

$$\sigma_i = (A^2 \Sigma_{11} + B^2 \Sigma_{22} + C^2 \Sigma_{33} + 2AB \Sigma_{12} + 2BC \Sigma_{23} + 2AC \Sigma_{13}) / \tau_{XY}^2 \tau_{YZ}^2$$

where $A = \tau_{XY} - \tau_{YZ} \cos \alpha$, $B = \tau_{YZ} - \tau_{XY} \cos \alpha$, $C = \tau_{XY} \tau_{YZ} \sin \alpha$ and τ 's denote the bonds.

(Table 1 Contd.)

$^{32}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$			
0	0.02991	0.05844	0.15399
298	0.03003 (0.03089)	0.05042 (0.03801)	0.17808 (0.16607)
500	0.03104	0.05613	0.21394
600	0.03190	0.05892	0.22984
700	0.03290	0.06275	0.24626
800	0.03401	0.06605	0.26159
900	0.03516	0.06929	0.27623
1000	0.03635	0.07245	0.29708
$^{34}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$			
0	0.02975	0.04800	0.16166
298	0.02986 (0.03088)	0.05000 (0.03827)	0.17823 (0.16601)
500	0.03084	0.05563	0.21341
600	0.03167	0.05889	0.23021
700	0.03265	0.06219	0.24629
800	0.03379	0.06543	0.26158
900	0.03487	0.06868	0.27460
1000	0.03604	0.07181	0.29022

Values in parenthesis are computed by the relation due to Muller *et al*⁸ and Morino *et al*⁹.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 lists the mean amplitude quantities for S-S (bonded), S-O (bonded) and S...O (non-bonded) distances at T=0 to 1000 K. Owing to the lack of space the symmetrized mean square amplitudes of disulfur monoxide isotopes could not be given here and can be had from the authors on request.

TABLE 1—MEAN AMPLITUDES OF VIBRATION FOR XYZ (O₂) TYPE OF MOLECULES

Temp. K	X-Y (Bonded)	Y-Z (bonded)	X...Z (non-bonded)
$^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$			
0	0.03019	0.04818	0.15398
298	0.03081 (0.03948)	0.05000 (0.03827)	0.17820 (0.16607)
500	0.03190	0.05554	0.21327
600	0.03214	0.05875	0.23004
700	0.03314	0.06201	0.24607
800	0.03424	0.06525	0.26135
900	0.03539	0.06843	0.27450
1000	0.03658	0.07154	0.29000
$^{34}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$			
0	0.03075	0.04633	0.15054
298	0.03089 (0.03948)	0.04814 (0.03730)	0.17602 (0.16585)
500	0.03202	0.05350	0.21146
600	0.3295	0.05659	0.22829
700	0.03403	0.05974	0.23694
800	0.03521	0.06286	0.25963
900	0.03645	0.06597	0.27995
1000	0.03770	0.06892	0.28815

In general, the S-S bonded mean amplitudes (0.030 Å) are found to be smaller than S-O bonded mean amplitudes (0.050 Å). These two mean amplitudes are found to be very small in comparison to non-bonded S...O mean amplitudes of vibration. In $^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$, if ^{16}O is replaced by ^{18}O it is found that S-S mean amplitudes remain constant but S-O bonded and S...O non-bonded mean amplitudes are decreased. Similarly, if we replace ^{32}S by ^{34}S the S-S mean amplitudes are reduced but S-O bonded and S...O non-bonded mean amplitudes remain practically the same. In a mixture of isotopic disulfur monoxide with ^{16}O ($^{32}\text{S}^{34}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$), if the substitution is made on Y atom only then also S-S mean amplitudes are found to decrease. However, in $^{34}\text{S}^{32}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$ system the effect of isotope substitution is more pronounced. The brief summary of the above statement is given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—ISOTOPE EFFECT ON MEAN AMPLITUDES AT T=298 K

Systems	l_{S-S}	l_{S-O}	$l_{S...O}$
$^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}/^{34}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$	0.0006	0.0018 (0.0010)	0.0022 (0.0002)
$^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}/^{34}\text{S}_2^{18}\text{O}$	nil	0.0004 (0.0090)	nil (0.0003)
$^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}/^{32}\text{S}^{34}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$	0.0003 (0.0086)	0.0004 (0.0003)	nil (0.0003)
$^{32}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}/^{34}\text{S}^{32}\text{S}^{16}\text{O}$	0.0004 (0.0086)	nil	nil

The values in parenthesis (Table 2) correspond to the isotope effect on mean amplitudes computed on the basis of relation involving force constant $f_r = 8.249$ mdyn/Å for S-O bond stretch, $f_r = 0.151$ mdyn/Å for non-bonded S...O, $f_r = 4.430$ mdyn/Å for S-S bond stretch reported by Hopkins *et al*⁶. The simple relation connecting force constant with bonded mean amplitude l_{x-y} in the case of isotopi-

$^{34}\text{S}_2^{16}\text{O}$			
0	0.02945	0.04335	0.15324
298	0.02957 (0.03051)	0.05042 (0.03801)	0.17811 (0.16601)
500	0.03057	0.05628	0.21145
600	0.03141	0.05962	0.23038
700	0.03240	0.06299	0.24650
800	0.03349	0.06633	0.26569
900	0.03463	0.06961	0.27651
1000	0.03580	0.07280	0.29055

cally substituted molecules due to Muller *et al*⁶ and Morino *et al*⁹ is as under :

$$l_{x-y}^2 = (0.4917 \times 10^{-2})/f_r + (1.0423 \times 10^{-2})(\mu_x + \mu_y)$$

where f_r is stretching force constant and μ_x and μ_y are the reciprocals of the masses of the X and Y atoms, respectively.

The mean amplitudes for bonded S-S and S-O distances for parent molecule is found to be 0.0303 Å and 0.0500 Å, respectively and for non-bonded S...O distances to be 0.1782 Å. These values, reported with the help of force constants, are in agreement with those computed by Σ -matrix formalism⁶ (see Table 1). It has been observed that the effect of ¹⁶O/¹⁸O substitution on bonded S-O mean amplitudes is more pronounced than due to ³²S/³⁴S substitution. In the former case the isotope effect for bonded S-O distance is found in the range of 0.0018 Å and in the latter case it is 0.0004 Å. Also for bonded S-S distance the isotope effects (Table 2) are 0.0006 Å in ³²S₂¹⁶O/³²S₂¹⁸O, 0.0007 Å in ³²S₂¹⁶O/³⁴S₂¹⁶O, 0.0003 Å in ³²S₂¹⁶O/³⁴S³²S¹⁶O pairs irrespective of the isotope substitution on sulfur or oxygen, the S-S bonded mean amplitudes lie in the range of 0.0003 Å to 0.0007 Å while for S-O distance the isotope effect is more sensitive to isotope and yields a value of 0.0018 Å in the case of ³²S₂¹⁶O/³²S₂¹⁸O (case of ¹⁶O/¹⁸O substitution) and reduces drastically to 0.0004 Å in the case of ³²S₂O/³⁴S₂O (case of ³²S/³⁴S substitution).

It has been noticed that S-O bonded mean amplitude as reported by Thirugnansambandam and

Mohan¹⁰ (0.0354 Å at T=298 K) in SO₂ is less than S-O bonded mean amplitude 0.04999 Å at the same temperature in S₂O. This shows that the S-O bond in S₂O is weaker than in SO₂ as is also clear from their corresponding force constants, f_r (S₂O)=8249 mdyn/Å (ref.4) and f_r (SO₂)=10.36 mdyn/Å (ref. 9). As far as S-S bonded mean amplitude in other forms of sulfur is concerned, it is also noticed that l_{S-S} in S₂O=0.035 Å is less than any other form, for example, in S₈ it is l_{S-S} =0.0547 Å as reported by Cyvin¹¹.

References

1. D. J. MESSCHI and R. J. MYERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 6220 ; *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1959, **3**, 405.
2. U. BLUKIS and R. J. MYERS, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, **69**, 1154.
3. P. W. SCHENK and R. STREUDL, in "Inorganic Sulfur Chemistry", (Ed.) G. NICKLESS, Elsevier, New York, N. Y., 1968, p. 367.
4. A. G. HOPKINS, F. P. DALY and C. W. BROWN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 1849.
5. S. J. CYVIN, "Molecular Vibrations and Mean Amplitudes", Universitetsforlaget, Oslo and Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968.
6. A. MULLER, B. KREBS and C. J. PRACOCK, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1968, **23a**, 1024.
7. S. J. CYVIN, "Molecular Structures and Vibrations", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1972.
8. E. TIEMANN, J. HOEFT, E. J. LOVAS and D. R. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, **60**, 5000.
9. Y. MORINO, K. KUCHITSU, A. TAKAHASHI and K. MACDA, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1958, **21**, 1927.
10. P. THIRUGNANSAMBANDAM and S. MOHAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1974, **61**, 470.
11. S. J. CYVIN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1970, **24**, 3259.